

Robust geometric feature extraction and classification

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ABSTRACT

This research proposes to use *geometric algebra* to systematically extract geometric features from data given in a vector space. We show the results of classification of hand-written digits, which were classified by feature extraction with the proposed method. Given a set of spatial vectors, we extract k -vectors (scalars, vectors, area elements, ...) of different subspace dimensions k ; which encode the variations of the features. Our results confirm that the strategy to mix different geometric algebra feature extractions is superior in both classification precision and robustness (e.g. against random rotations) when compared with pure coordinate value features, which is the most often used conventional method.

1 Introduction

Nowadays, enormous amounts of data are available in various fields, therefore data mining which analyzes data to reveal interesting information becomes more and more necessary. But so far most conventional methods of feature extraction ignore the *geometric properties* of data even when data have spatial features. For example, when m vectors are measured from an object in three-dimensional space, conventional methods represent the object by $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^{3m}$ which is the vector made by arranging m groups of 3 coordinates of each vector in a row.

However, because these coordinate values depend on the definition of the coordinate system, inference or classification becomes remarkably bad, when objects are measured in a coordinate system different from the one used for learning. Furthermore, spatial information of the object in three-dimensional space is lost when each element $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^{3m}$ is, for example, normalized. Some conventional methods may extract coordinate-free features, but whether such features arise, are complete, and are adopted depends on the experience of the model builder.

In this study [1], we use *geometric algebra* (GA) which can describe spatial vectors and all higher order subspace relations between them [2–4], to systematically undertake various kinds of feature extractions, and to improve precision and robustness in classification problems. There are already many successful examples of its use in image processing, signal processing, colored image processing, or multi-dimensional time-series signal processing with complex numbers or quaternions, which are low dimensional GAs [5–11]. In addition, GA-valued neural network learning methods for learning input-output relationships [12–14] are well studied. Further engineering applications of GA can be found in [15, 16].

In our proposed method, geometric features extracted with GA [17] can also be used for learning a data distribution. In this study, we use geometric features to learn a Gaussian mixture model (GMM) with the expectation maximization (EM) algorithm [18], and apply this to a classification problem. Because each feature extraction derived by the proposed method has its own advantages and disadvantages, we apply a plural mixture of GMMs for the classification problem. As an example of multi-class classification of geometric

data, we use a hand-written digit dataset of the UCI Machine Learning Repository [19].

When classifying new hand-written digits in practice with the learning model, it is natural to expect that the coordinate system in a real new environment differs from the one used for obtaining the learning dataset. Therefore, in this paper, we evaluate the classification performance for randomly rotated test data.

2 Method

2.1 Geometric products of vectors

Definition 1 (Clifford geometric algebra) A

Clifford geometric algebra $\mathcal{G}_{p,q}$ is defined by the associative geometric product of elements of a quadratic vector space $\mathbb{R}^{p,q}$, their linear combination and closure. $\mathcal{G}_{p,q}$ includes the field of real numbers \mathbb{R} and the vector space $\mathbb{R}^{p,q}$ as subspaces. The geometric product of two vectors is defined as

$$\mathbf{ab} = \mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{b} + \mathbf{a} \wedge \mathbf{b}, \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{b}$ indicates the standard inner product and the bivector $\mathbf{a} \wedge \mathbf{b}$ indicates Grassmann's antisymmetric outer product. $\mathbf{a} \wedge \mathbf{b}$ can be geometrically interpreted as the oriented parallelogram area spanned by the vectors \mathbf{a} and \mathbf{b} . Geometric algebras are graded, with grades (subspace dimensions) ranging from zero (scalars) to $n = p + q$ (pseudoscalars, n -volumes).

The geometric algebra $\mathcal{G}_3 = \mathcal{G}_{3,0}$ of three-dimensional Euclidean space $\mathbb{R}^3 = \mathbb{R}^{3,0}$ has an eight-dimensional basis of scalars (grade 0), vectors (grade 1), bivectors (grade 2) and trivectors (grade 3). Trivectors in \mathcal{G}_3 are also referred to as oriented volumes or pseudoscalars. Using an orthonormal basis $\{\mathbf{e}_1, \mathbf{e}_2, \mathbf{e}_3\}$ for \mathbb{R}^3 we can write the basis of \mathcal{G}_3 as

$$\{1, \mathbf{e}_1, \mathbf{e}_2, \mathbf{e}_3, \mathbf{e}_2\mathbf{e}_3, \mathbf{e}_3\mathbf{e}_1, \mathbf{e}_1\mathbf{e}_2, i = \mathbf{e}_1\mathbf{e}_2\mathbf{e}_3\}. \quad (2)$$

In (2) i is the unit trivector, i.e. the oriented volume of a unit cube. Let us point out, that the even subalgebra \mathcal{G}_3^+ of \mathcal{G}_3 is isomorphic to the quaternions \mathbb{H} of Hamilton. We therefore call elements of \mathcal{G}_3^+ rotors (shorthand for rotation operators), because they can be used to implement rotations

of vectors (and all other elements) of \mathcal{G}_3 . The role of quaternion conjugation is naturally taken by reversion

$$\begin{aligned} (\mathbf{a}_1 \mathbf{a}_2 \dots \mathbf{a}_s)^\sim &= \mathbf{a}_s \dots \mathbf{a}_2 \mathbf{a}_1, \\ \mathbf{a}_1, \mathbf{a}_2, \dots, \mathbf{a}_s &\in \mathbb{R}^{p,q}, \quad s \in \mathbb{N}. \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

The inverse of a non-null vector \mathbf{a} with respect to the geometric product is defined as

$$\mathbf{a}^{-1} = \frac{\mathbf{a}}{\mathbf{a}^2}. \quad (4)$$

A reflection at a hyperplane with normal vector $\mathbf{a} \in \mathbb{R}^{p,q}$ can be formulated as

$$\mathbf{x}' = -\mathbf{a}^{-1} \mathbf{x} \mathbf{a}. \quad (5)$$

A rotation by the angle θ in the plane of a unit bivector i_2 can thus be given as the product $R = \mathbf{ab}$ of two vectors \mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b} from the i_2 -plane (i.e. geometrically as a sequence of two reflections) with angle $\theta/2$.

Blades of grade k , $0 \leq k \leq n = p + q$ are the outer products of k vectors \mathbf{a}_l ($1 \leq l \leq k$) and directly represent the k -dimensional vector subspaces V spanned by the set of vectors \mathbf{a}_l ($1 \leq l \leq k$). This subspace representation is also called outer product null space (OPNS) representation.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{x} \in V &= \text{span}[\mathbf{a}_l, 1 \leq l \leq k] \\ \Leftrightarrow \mathbf{x} \wedge \mathbf{a}_1 \wedge \mathbf{a}_2 \wedge \dots \wedge \mathbf{a}_k &= 0. \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Extracting a certain grade part from the geometric product of two blades A_k and B_l has a deep geometric meaning.

One example is the grade $l - k$ part of the geometric product $A_k B_l$, that represents the orthogonal complement of A_k in B_l , provided that A_k is contained in B_l

$$A_k \lrcorner B_l = \langle A_k B_l \rangle_{l-k} \quad (7)$$

Because of its geometrical significance this grade part is called contraction [4] of A_k on B_l .

Another important grade part of the geometric product of A_k and B_l is the maximum grade $l + k$ part, also called the outer product part

$$A_k \wedge B_l = \langle A_k B_l \rangle_{l+k}. \quad (8)$$

If $A_k \wedge B_l$ is non-zero it represents the union of the disjoint (except for the zero vector) subspaces represented by A_k and B_l .

2.2 Geometric feature extraction

Now we propose a systematic derivation of feature extractions from a *set* or a *series* of spatial vectors $\xi = \{\mathbf{p}_l \in \mathbb{R}^n, l = 1, \dots, m\}$. Our method is to extract k -vectors of different grades k ; which encode the variations of the features [17].

First, assuming ξ is an ordered *series* of n -dimensional vectors, $n' + 1$ feature extractions are derived where $n' = \min\{n, m\}$. For $I = i_1 \dots i_k$, $\mathbf{e}_I^{-1} = \mathbf{e}_{i_k} \dots \mathbf{e}_{i_2} \mathbf{e}_{i_1}$. We define

$$f_0(\xi) = \{\langle \mathbf{p}_l \mathbf{p}_{l+1} \rangle, l = 1, \dots, n' - 1\} \in \mathbb{R}^{m-1}, \quad (9)$$

where $\langle \mathbf{p}_l \mathbf{p}_{l+1} \rangle = \langle \mathbf{p}_l \mathbf{p}_{l+1} \rangle_0 = \mathbf{p}_l \cdot \mathbf{p}_{l+1}$ is the scalar part of the geometric product of the vectors $\mathbf{p}_l, \mathbf{p}_{l+1}$, i.e. their inner product.

For $k = 1, \dots, n'$, we write $k' = k - 1$,

$$f_k(\xi) = \{\langle \mathbf{p}_l \dots \mathbf{p}_{l+k'} \mathbf{e}_I^{-1} \rangle, I \in \mathcal{I}_k, l = 1, \dots, n' - k'\} \in \mathbb{R}^{(m-k')|\mathcal{I}_k|}, \quad (10)$$

where, $|\mathcal{I}_k|$ is the number of combinations of k elements from n elements, and \mathbf{e}_I^{-1} is the inverse of \mathbf{e}_I .

Next, assuming that ξ is a *set* of vectors, $n' + 1$ feature extractions can also be derived in the same way

$$f_0(\xi) = \{\langle \mathbf{p}_{l_1} \mathbf{p}_{l_2} \rangle\} \in \mathbb{R}^{mC_2}, \quad (11)$$

$$f_k(\xi) = \{\langle \mathbf{p}_{l_1} \dots \mathbf{p}_{l_k} \mathbf{e}_I^{-1} \rangle, I \in \mathcal{I}_k\} \in \mathbb{R}^{(mC_k)|\mathcal{I}_k|}, \quad (12)$$

where mC_k is the number of combinations when we choose k elements from m elements. The dimension of the feature space becomes different from the case where ξ is a series.

Below we show several feature extractions for the case of hand-written digit data of the UCI Repository [19]. Each of the digit data is given by eight points $\xi = \{\mathbf{p}_1, \dots, \mathbf{p}_8\}$, measured by dividing the hand-written curves in seven equally long curve segments. Each two-dimensional point is given by $\mathbf{p}_l = x_l \mathbf{e}_1 + y_l \mathbf{e}_2$ with centering $\sum_{l=1}^8 x_l = \sum_{l=1}^8 y_l = 0$. Using GA, the feature extraction can be undertaken systematically. Fig. 1 shows some examples of the handwritten

digit '1'. In this figure straight line segments from point to point, replace the real curved trajectories of a pen.

Fig. 1 Examples of hand-written digit '1'.

A first feature extraction f_0 uses the *inner product* (including the cosine of the enclosed angle) of consecutive point vectors

$$f_0(\xi) = [\langle \mathbf{p}_1 \mathbf{p}_2 \rangle, \dots, \langle \mathbf{p}_7 \mathbf{p}_8 \rangle] = [x_1 x_2 + y_1 y_2, \dots, x_7 x_8 + y_7 y_8] \in \mathbb{R}^7. \quad (13)$$

The second simple (coordinate) feature extraction f_1 , which is also used in conventional methods, is

$$f_1(\xi) = [\langle \mathbf{p}_1 \mathbf{e}_1^{-1} \rangle, \langle \mathbf{p}_1 \mathbf{e}_2^{-1} \rangle, \dots, \langle \mathbf{p}_8 \mathbf{e}_1^{-1} \rangle, \langle \mathbf{p}_8 \mathbf{e}_2^{-1} \rangle] = [\mathbf{p}_1 \cdot \mathbf{e}_1, \mathbf{p}_1 \cdot \mathbf{e}_2, \dots, \mathbf{p}_8 \cdot \mathbf{e}_1, \mathbf{p}_8 \cdot \mathbf{e}_2] = [x_1, y_1, \dots, x_8, y_8] \in \mathbb{R}^{16}. \quad (14)$$

A third feature extraction f_2 uses the directed magnitudes of *outer products* (including the sine of the enclosed angle) of consecutive point vectors,

$$f_2(\xi) = [\langle \mathbf{p}_1 \mathbf{p}_2 \mathbf{e}_{12}^{-1} \rangle, \dots, \langle \mathbf{p}_7 \mathbf{p}_8 \mathbf{e}_{12}^{-1} \rangle] = [x_1 y_2 - x_2 y_1, \dots, x_7 y_8 - x_8 y_7] \in \mathbb{R}^7, \quad (15)$$

where $\langle \mathbf{p}_1 \mathbf{p}_2 \mathbf{e}_{12}^{-1} \rangle = \pm |\mathbf{p}_1 \wedge \mathbf{p}_2|$ represents the signed magnitude of the parallelogram area spanned by \mathbf{p}_1 and \mathbf{p}_2 .

2.3 Data distribution learning for multi-class classification

A *Gaussian mixture model* (GMM) is useful to approximate a data distribution in a data space. A GMM is characterized by a set of three parameters $\Theta = \{\beta_j, \mu_j, \Sigma_j\}$, where β_j , μ_j and Σ_j are the *mixture ratio*, the *mean vector*, and the *variance covariance matrix* of the j -th Gaussian distribution, respectively. The *output* is

$$p(\xi | \Theta) = \sum_{j=1}^M \beta_j \mathcal{N}_d(f(\xi) - \mu_j; \Sigma_j), \quad (16)$$

where $\mathcal{N}_d(\cdot; \cdot)$ is the d -dimensional Gaussian distribution function whose center is fixed at the origin.

To train M Gaussians with given incomplete data $X = \{x_i = f(\xi_i) \mid 1 \leq i \leq N\}$, the expectation maximization (EM) algorithm [18] is often utilized. The algorithm identifies both the parameters Θ and *latent variables* $Z = \{z_{ij} \in \{0, 1\} \mid 1 \leq j \leq M\}$. The z_{ij} are random variables, which for $z_{ij} = 1$ indicate that the individual datum x_i belongs the j -th of M Gaussian distributions. Thus $\sum_{j=1}^M P(z_{ij}) = 1$.

The EM algorithm repeats the *expectation* E-step and the *maximization* M-step until both $P(Z)$ and Θ converge. The *E-step* updates the probabilities of Z according to Bayes' theorem $P(Z | X, \Theta) \propto p(X | Z, \Theta)$. The *M-step* updates the parameters Θ of the Gaussians to maximize the likelihood $l(\Theta, X, Z) = p(X | Z, \Theta)$.

A major drawback of the GMM is its large number of free parameters whose order is $O(Md^2)$. Moreover when the correlation between any pair of features is close to 1, the calculation of the inverse matrix is numerically unstable. To remedy this, Tipping and Bishop [20] proposed to use only the eigenvectors with the largest q eigenvalues, where q is a preset value of a Gaussian distribution. But the number of free parameters is not necessarily the same for different Gaussian distributions. With fixed q therefore the GMM produces a bad approximation of a probability distribution.

To improve this, Meinicke and Ritter [21] proposed to use only the eigenvectors of Gaussian distributions which are larger than a certain *cutoff*. The cutoff eigenvalue is set at $\lambda_- =$

Fig. 2 Flow of multi-class classification. Top: Training of the GMM for class $C \in \{‘0’, \dots, ‘9’\}$. The D_{1C} denotes a subset of training samples whose label is C . The $f : \xi \mapsto x$ shows feature extraction. Either of $\{f_0, f_1, f_2\}$ is chosen as f . Bottom: Estimation by the learned GMMs. The same f chosen for training is used here. The GMM_C outputs $p(\xi | C)$. The final estimation is $C^* = \arg \max_C p(\xi | C) P(C)$, $P(C)$ is the prior distribution. D_3 is the independent test data set.

$\alpha \lambda_{\max}$, where $\alpha \in (0, 1]$ is a hyper parameter and λ_{\max} is the largest eigenvalue of the variance covariance matrix of incomplete data X . It means that we approximate eq. (16) by

$$p(x | \Theta) = \sum_{j=1}^M \beta_j \prod_{k=1}^d \mathcal{N}_1((x - \mu_j) \cdot v_k; \lambda_k) \approx \sum_{j=1}^M \beta_j \left\{ \prod_{k=1}^{q_j} \mathcal{N}_1((x - \mu_j) \cdot v_k; \lambda_k) \right\} \times \{ \mathcal{N}_1((x - \mu_j)_-; \lambda_-) \}^{d - q_j}, \quad (17)$$

where, λ_k is the k -th largest eigenvalue of the j -th Gaussian distribution. The v_k is the corresponding eigenvector. Because $k \leq q_j \Leftrightarrow \lambda_k > \lambda_-$, the bracket $(x - \mu_j)_-$ is the length of the component, which is perpendicular to the q_j eigenvectors with the largest eigenvalues.

The flow of training and estimation of handwritten digit classification, as an example of multi-class classification, is shown in Fig. 2. The M and α for each GMM are decided by validation with dataset D_2 .

2.4 Mixture of experts

Each feature extraction derived with GA has advantages and disadvantages. A big merit of adopt-

ing *learning of distributions* rather than learning of input-output relations is that the learned distributions allow us to obtain reliable inference by *mixing* plural (several) weak learners. In this study, we therefore use a mixture of GMMs. Inferences are mixed as

$$p(\xi | C) = \prod_{k=0}^2 p(f_k(\xi) | C). \quad (18)$$

Fig. 3 shows the mixture of different GMMs. Inferences via different feature extractions are mixed to produce the output $p(\xi | C)$.

Fig. 3 Mixture of GMMs. Three GMMs via different feature extractions are mixed to yield output $p(\xi | C)$.

3 Experimental results and discussion

3.1 Classification of hand-written digits

We used the Pen-Based Recognition of Hand-written Digits dataset (Pendigits dataset in the following) of the UCI Repository [19] as an example application for multi-class classification because digits have two-dimensional spatial features. The Pendigits dataset consists of 10992 samples written by 44 people. Among these samples 7494 samples were written by 30 people, divided into learning data D_1 , and validation data D_2 . The 3498 remaining samples were written by 14 other people and are used as test data D_3 .

In the sample collection, the pen point coordinates at 100 msec intervals were measured on a tablet with a resolution of 500×500 pixels. Eight points $\{r_l\}$ dividing the orbit of the pen point into seven equally long segments were chosen, and *scaled* so that both the horizontal and vertical ranges became $[0, 100]$. The aspect ratio changes when scaling, and thus some original geometric information is lost. In this study, we carry out the feature extraction with GA, after computing

$p_l = r_l - \bar{r}$, i.e. setting the origin \bar{r} at the center of the digit.

3.2 Classification result of feature extraction and mixture of experts

For each feature extraction $f \in \{f_0, f_1, f_2\}$, the GMM learned from D_1 with 4 values of $\alpha \in \{0.1, 0.01, 0.001, 0.0001\}$ and we then evaluated the correct classification rate for D_2 . Table 1 shows the results. In Table 1, the maximal classification rate is underlined. $\alpha = 0.01$ was therefore chosen for all feature extractions $\{f_0, f_1, f_2\}$.

Table 1 Correct classification rate for D_2 for various α .

α	f_1	f_2	f_0
0.1	93.22%	95.09%	84.08%
0.01	<u>99.36%</u>	<u>96.53%</u>	<u>90.13%</u>
0.001	99.28%	96.43%	89.44%
0.0001	98.88%	96.45%	89.78%

Table 2 shows the results of the identified models and the number of misclassifications via inner products f_0 . The total number of misclassifications was 494 and the correct classification rate was 85.88%.

Table 3 shows the results of the identified models M , with $\bar{q} = \frac{\sum_j q_j}{M}$ and the number of misclassifications via coordinates f_1 . In Table 3, e.g. the cell of column ‘0’ and row ‘8’ shows 11 samples of ‘0’ data which were misclassified to ‘8’. The total number of misclassifications was 100 and the correct classification rate was 97.14%.

Table 4 shows the results of the identified models and the number of misclassifications via outer products f_2 . The total number of misclassifications was 201 and the correct classification rate was 94.25%.

Tables 2, 3, and 4 clearly show the differences in the misclassifications by the different feature extractions. Because the feature extraction f_1 keeps the coordinate information of each point, it results in a smaller number of misclassifications. But it has other disadvantages. For example, because the first point p_1 of most learning data of ‘0’ is in the top left area, some test data whose p_1 is in the top right area, are misclassified.

Table 2 Identified models and number of misclassifications via inner products f_0 .

	'0'	'1'	'2'	'3'	'4'	'5'	'6'	'7'	'8'	'9'
M	2	8	9	4	4	8	6	6	5	5
\bar{q}	6.5	4.9	4.8	6.3	6	5.1	5.3	4.8	6.6	6.8
'0'	-							1		1
'1'		-	9	2	7	5		1	9	4
'2'	1	13	-	15	16	9		2		1
'3'		8	8	-	4	5			1	5
'4'		12	35	3	-	5		4	11	9
'5'	5	6	4	29	1	-		3	10	23
'6'	5	6	1		4		-	8	4	5
'7'		16	4	2	12		20	-	19	3
'8'	2	3			7	13	2	14	-	2
'9'	1	30	1	1	4	14		1	3	-

Table 3 Identified models and number of misclassifications via coordinates f_1 .

	'0'	'1'	'2'	'3'	'4'	'5'	'6'	'7'	'8'	'9'
M	6	7	5	5	5	8	7	6	8	9
\bar{q}	6	6.1	8.4	9.4	8.4	3	6.4	7.8	7.5	8.7
'0'	-						1		11	
'1'		-	3							
'2'		2	-					1		
'3'		1		-		1		2		1
'4'					-	10				1
'5'				2		-				4
'6'						2	-		2	
'7'		32		3				-	3	
'8'						1			-	
'9'		3				10		3	1	-

Table 4 Identified models and number of misclassifications via outer products f_2 .

	'0'	'1'	'2'	'3'	'4'	'5'	'6'	'7'	'8'	'9'
M	2	7	3	3	3	4	3	6	7	8
\bar{q}	7	4.2	5.3	6	7	4.7	5.3	5.5	5.1	5.5
'0'	-									
'1'		-	9	2	6			10		1
'2'		5	-					1	1	
'3'		5		-		1				1
'4'					-		3		2	9
'5'		1		4	15	-			1	17
'6'	1				4		-		1	11
'7'		30	6	2				-	4	7
'8'									-	2
'9'		1		5		23		9	6	-

Table 5 Number of misclassifications by mixture of experts.

	'0'	'1'	'2'	'3'	'4'	'5'	'6'	'7'	'8'	'9'
'0'	-								6	
'1'		-	4							
'2'		4	-							
'3'		2		-		1				
'4'					-	3				
'5'				4		-				3
'6'							-		4	
'7'		28		4				-	2	1
'8'									-	
'9'		3				2		3	1	-

The feature extractions f_0 and f_2 , on the other hand, lose the coordinate information of each point. But they extract *partial shape features* not affected (invariant) by the position of the part of the digit under concern. Therefore f_0 and f_2 correctly classified the '0' data with curves beginning in the top right area. Therefore, a *mixture* of different f_0, f_1, f_2 expert feature extractions works best.

Table 5 shows the number of misclassifications using a mixture of experts. The total number of misclassifications was 75 and the correct classification rate was 97.86%, both *better* than the result of only using f_0, f_1 or f_2 .

3.3 Robustness against measurement environment fluctuation

We assumed cases of *different measurement environments* from the one in which both D_1 and D_2 have been measured. We generated a dataset $D'_3 = \{R(\xi, \varphi), \xi \in D_3, \varphi \sim \mathcal{U}(\varepsilon)\}$ that randomly rotated each digit of the test data D_3 . $\mathcal{U}(\varepsilon)$ is a uniform distribution of $[-\varepsilon, \varepsilon]$ and φ is a random variable. We generated 20 different sets D'_3 from the test dataset D_3 for each $\varepsilon \in \{\frac{\pi}{40}, \frac{\pi}{20}, \frac{\pi}{10}\}$ and classified them. $R(\xi, \theta)$ rotates all the points of ξ by θ . Fig. 4 shows the average and the standard deviation of the correct classification rate when using the feature extraction f_1 and the mixture of experts.

The classification precision using only feature extraction f_1 decreased remarkably with increasing ε . On the other hand, the classification precision using the mixture of expert did not decrease

Fig. 4 Correct classification rate with f_1 and mixture of experts.

that much. The rotations had *no influence* in the cases of f_0 and f_2 .

4 Conclusions

In this study, we proposed systematic feature extraction methods by using GA. To the extracted features, we applied the classification of the hand-written digits by using GMMs. We applied the proposed method to two-dimensional objects of hand-written digits deriving three ways of feature extraction, via inner products, coordinates, and outer products.

The classification success rate using coordinate value feature extraction was higher than only using outer product feature extraction or inner product feature extraction. However, when we assumed cases of different measurement environments, the classification success rate by pure coordinate value feature extraction dropped substantially for rotated test data.

In contrast to this, with the mixture of experts, the classification success rate was not only *higher* in the case of a constant measurement environment, it was also much more *stable* in the case of large rotations of the test data.

Therefore, our *results* confirm that the strategy to mix different GA feature extractions is superior in both classification *precision* and *robustness* when compared with pure coordinate value features, which is the most often used conventional method.

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